

Thermodynamic studies of cadmium sulphate in aqueous mannitol from electromotive force measurements

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The standard molal potentials (E_m^\ominus) of the cell, Cd-Hg | CdSO₄ (m), mannitol (x) | Hg₂SO₄ (s) | Hg, have been determined in water and 5, 15 and 25% aqueous mannitol solutions at five different temperatures (298–318 K) and molality of cadmium sulphate ranged from 0.01 to 0.1 mol kg⁻¹. Mean molal activity coefficients at 298 K are calculated. The temperature variation of the standard e.m.f. is used to calculate the standard thermodynamic functions (ΔG^\ominus) for the cell reaction. The primary medium effect of different solvents upon cadmium sulphate and standard quantities of transfer for cadmium sulphate from the standard state in water to that in the respective aqueous mannitol solutions are also calculated.

The thermodynamic functions of transfer of solute from one solvent to another can be determined with the help of electromotive force measurements. The signs of transfer functions have been considered as the sole criteria of knowing the structural status of the solvent. The present investigations have been carried out to determine the activity coefficients of cadmium sulphate in aqueous mannitol solutions under varied conditions and to evaluate the thermodynamic functions of transfer from water to respective aqueous mannitol solutions. Cadmium sulphate is chosen as electrolyte because of easy and reliable setting up of the cell. Aqueous mannitol is the chosen solvent as carbohydrate and related polyhydroxy compounds are the important constituents of biological systems. An understanding of the solution behaviour of aqueous systems involving carbohydrates and polyhydroxy compounds can be seen as an essential pre-requisite to a full understanding of the solution behaviour of the complex processes occurring in the biological systems.

Results and Discussion

The standard molal potentials (E_m^\ominus) of the cell, Cd-Hg | CdSO₄ (m), mannitol (x) | Hg₂SO₄ (s) | Hg, in different solutions have been estimated from equation (1)¹,

$$E_o' = E + k \log m - k \left(\frac{A z^+ z^- I^{1/2}}{1 + Ba_o I^{1/2}} \right) = E_m^\ominus - kB'I \quad (1)$$

where E is the observed e.m.f., I the ionic strength of the solution, m the molality of the solution, A and B are Debye-Hückel constants, a_o is the ion size parameter, z^+ and z^- are the valencies of cation and anion respectively, k equals to $2.3026 RT/F$ and B' is a constant and is a measure of interaction energy² for a particular cation-anion combination. The values of the Debye-Hückel constants for the various mannitol + water solutions at different temperatures have been calculated³ by using the relations (2) and (3),

$$A = \left(\frac{2 \pi N}{1000} \right)^{1/2} \cdot \frac{e^3}{2.3026 k^{3/2}} \cdot \frac{1}{(DT)^{3/2}} \quad (2)$$

$$B = \left(\frac{8 \pi N e^2}{1000k} \right)^{1/2} \cdot \frac{1}{(DT)^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

where D is the dielectric constant⁴ of the solvent, N the Avogadro number, k the Boltzmann constant and e the electronic charge.

From equation (1) it is expected that E_o' should be a linear function of I when a suitable value of ion-size parameter is used. The values of a_o for different solvent mixtures at different temperatures are chosen in such a way that the deviation from linearity of the plot of E_o' against I is minimum. A deviation of ± 0.2 mV in E_m^\ominus was seen when a_o values were varied within $\pm 0.3 \text{ \AA}$ of the chosen values. The ion size parameter which gave a satisfactory linear extrapolation were in the range 5.0–5.2 \AA . The intercept of the plot at $I \rightarrow 0$ then gives the value of standard molal potential of the cell (E_m^\ominus). The values of E_m^\ominus of different mannitol + water solutions are given in Table 1. The average standard deviation in E_m^\ominus is ± 0.5 mV for cadmium sulphate in mannitol + water mixtures.

Table 1. Standard molal potentials (E_m^\ominus , V) of the cell used in mannitol + water mixtures at different temperatures

Mannitol wt. %	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K
0	0.7693	0.7612	0.7533	0.7455	0.7379
5	0.7638	0.7556	0.7475	0.7394	0.7316
15	0.7576	0.7491	0.7405	0.7319	0.7231
25	0.7506	0.7417	0.7328	0.7236	0.7144

The values of activity coefficients (λ_\pm) of the cadmium sulphate in various mannitol + water solutions can be calculated from equation (4)⁵,

$$E = E_m^0 - k \log m \lambda_{\pm} \quad (4)$$

The value of λ_{\pm} for cadmium sulphate in water is comparable with the literature value³ at 298 K which is 0.150 for 0.1 *m* CdSO₄ solution. The activity coefficients of cadmium sulphate in mannitol + water solutions at 298 K are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Mean molal activity coefficients (λ_{\pm}) of cadmium sulphate in different mannitol + water mixtures at 298 K

Concn. mol kg ⁻¹	Mannitol (wt. %)			
	0	5	15	25
0.01	0.427	0.433	0.418	0.413
0.02	0.414	0.410	0.404	0.390
0.04	0.286	0.285	0.280	0.277
0.06	0.234	0.233	0.229	0.225
0.08	0.190	0.191	0.187	0.182
0.10	0.158	0.164	0.156	0.155

The activity coefficients of cadmium sulphate at a particular molality found to decrease with increasing mannitol content, as expected from Debye-Hückel theory, is due to lowering of dielectric constant of the medium. The higher magnitude of the activity coefficients at lower mannitol content suggests that the solute-solvent interaction increases as the mannitol content decreases.

The E_m^0 values are fitted by the method of least-squares to equation (5),

$$E_m^0 = a - b(T-298) - c(T-298)^2 \quad (5)$$

where T is the temperature (K). The values of the constants a , b and c for cadmium sulphate in mannitol + water are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3. Values of the constants a , b and c of equation (5)

Mannitol wt. %	a	b	c
	V	10 ⁻⁴ VK ⁻¹	10 ⁻⁶ VK ⁻²
0	0.7694	16.54	-4
5	0.7638	16.59	-2.2
15	0.7576	17.03	1
25	0.7506	17.73	1.8

The standard thermodynamic function, standard free energy change (ΔG^0) for the cell reaction,

have been calculated from the temperature variation of the standard molal potential in mannitol + water solvent using equation (6),

$$\Delta G^0 = -nFE_m^0 = -2F[a - b(T-298) - c(T-298)^2] \quad (6)$$

The ΔG^0 values for the cell reaction at different temperatures in mannitol + water are recorded in Table 4. It has been found that ΔG^0 for the cell reaction is negative and it increases with increase in temperature of the solvent system as well as with increase in mannitol content in the solvent mixture. It can be attributed to the decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium.

Table 4. Standard molal thermodynamic function (ΔG^0 , kJ mol⁻¹) of the cell reaction in different mannitol + water solutions and temperatures

T K	Mannitol (wt. %)			
	0	5	15	25
298	148.5	147.4	146.2	144.9
303	146.9	145.8	144.6	143.1
308	145.4	144.3	142.9	141.4
313	143.9	142.7	141.3	139.7
318	142.4	141.2	139.6	137.9

The primary medium effect ($\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0$) is a measure of the change of Gibbs free energy which accompanies the transfer of one mole of cadmium sulphate from the standard state in water to the standard state in mannitol + water. Thus, it is a measure of escaping tendency of cadmium sulphate from standard state in mannitol + water to standard state in water. The primary medium effect, $\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0$ (mole fraction scale) of mannitol + water solvent upon cadmium sulphate was computed by the usual relations⁶ at different temperatures by equation (7),

$$\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0 = (E_{m,w}^0 - E_{m,s}^0) / 2k \quad (7)$$

where $E_{m,w}^0$ is the standard e.m.f. of the cell in water and $E_{m,s}^0$ in mannitol + water solvent. The values of $\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0$ are given in Table 5. It is clear from the data that the escaping tendency of cadmium sulphate is greater in mannitol + water solvents than in water. It is because the primary medium effect of mannitol + water mixtures on cadmium sulphate increases with increase in percentage of mannitol. It is also found that with increasing temperature, the escaping tendency increases.

The standard thermodynamic quantities of transfer from water to mannitol + water solvent are evaluated with the help of the relations⁶ at different temperatures on the mole fraction scale to eliminate the Gibbs free energy change as a result of concentration changes in the transfer process⁷. The standard change of Gibbs free energy (ΔG_i^0) can be represented as a function of temperature (K) by equation (8),

Table 5. Primary medium effect, $\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0$ (mole fraction scale) of mannitol + water solvents upon CdSO₄ at different temperatures and values of constants A , B and C of equation (9) for evaluation of thermodynamic quantities for transfer of CdSO₄ from water to mannitol + water

Mannitol wt. %	$\log {}^s_w \gamma_{\pm}^0$					A	B	C
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K			
5	0.047	0.047	0.048	0.049	0.050	22.63	-14.79	0.25
15	0.099	0.101	0.105	0.110	0.117	88.75	-59.17	1.00
25	0.159	0.163	0.168	0.177	0.186	108.17	-72.30	1.24

$$-2F[(E_m^{\theta})_s - (E_m^{\theta})_w] - 2 \times 2.3026RT \log \left(\frac{M_s}{M_w} \right) = \Delta G_t^{\theta} = A + BT + CT^2 \quad (8)$$

where M_s and M_w are the molecular weights of solvent (mannitol + water) and water respectively. The least-square values of constants A , B and C are given in Table 5. By application of usual thermodynamic relations to equation (8), the following expressions for the standard changes of enthalpy (ΔH_t^{θ}), entropy (ΔS_t^{θ}) and heat capacity (ΔC_p^{θ}) for the transfer process of cadmium sulphate from water to mannitol + water has been derived,

$$-d(\Delta G_t^{\theta})/dT = \Delta S_t^{\theta} = -(B + 2CT) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta G_t^{\theta} + T\Delta S_t^{\theta} = \Delta H_t^{\theta} = A - CT^2 \quad (10)$$

$$d(\Delta G_t^{\theta})/dT = \Delta C_p^{\theta} = -2CT \quad (11)$$

The standard thermodynamic quantities of transfer calculated from above equations are reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Standard thermodynamic quantities for the transfer of cadmium sulphate from water to mannitol + water mixtures at different temperatures

Mannitol wt. %	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K
	ΔG_t^{θ} (kJ mol ⁻¹)				
5	0.84	0.86	0.88	0.93	0.98
15	1.54	1.61	1.72	1.88	2.08
25	2.35	2.49	2.65	2.90	3.18
	$-\Delta H_t^{\theta}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)				
5	0.35	0.40	1.17	1.95	2.74
15	0.37	3.39	6.45	9.57	12.74
25	1.52	5.24	9.01	12.84	16.74
	$-\Delta S_t^{\theta}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)				
5	1.65	4.16	6.67	9.17	11.68
15	6.46	16.50	26.54	36.57	46.61
25	13.13	25.48	37.84	50.19	62.54
	$-\Delta C_p^{\theta}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)				
5	149.5	152.0	154.6	157.1	159.6
15	598.1	608.2	618.2	628.3	638.3
25	736.2	748.5	760.9	773.2	785.6

The values of ΔG_t^{θ} are found to be positive for all the solvent compositions and they increase with increasing temperature as well as the mannitol content in the solvent mixture. Positive ΔG_t^{θ} values suggest that cadmium sulphate is in a higher free energy state in mannitol + water mixtures than in water, and the transfer of cadmium sulphate from water to mannitol + water mixtures is not a spontaneous process with the solutes in the standard state in mannitol + water.

The values of ΔS_t^{θ} and ΔH_t^{θ} are negative for all the solvent mixtures at different temperatures. The negative values suggest that the tendency of order created by cadmium sulphate in aqueous mannitol is more than in pure water at all the temperatures studied. Cadmium sulphate thus breaks more structure in water than in mannitol +

water solvent⁸. This is further supported by the view⁹ that all structure-forming processes including solvation of ions are exothermic and are accompanied by a loss of entropy. It has also been found that ΔH_t^{θ} decreases with increasing mannitol content, suggesting that association in mannitol + water decreases with increasing temperature and also with increasing mannitol content. ΔC_p^{θ} values are found to be negative and they decrease with increasing temperature as well as mannitol content in the medium.

As the transfer process involves the transfer of charged particles, viz. Cd^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} ions from water to mannitol + water mixtures, i.e. solvent having different dielectric constants, it is convenient to split ΔG_t^{θ} values into two parts¹⁰, an electrostatic part, $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ corresponding to change in dielectric constant of the medium and a non-electrostatic or chemical part, $\Delta G_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta}$ arising from specific chemical interactions between ions and the solvent.

Thus,

$$\Delta G_t^{\theta} = \Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} + \Delta G_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta} \quad (12)$$

$\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ has been estimated from Born equation (14)¹¹,

$$\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{D_s} - \frac{1}{D_w} \right] \left[\frac{1}{r_+} + \frac{1}{r_-} \right] \quad (13)$$

where N is the Avogadro's number, D_s and D_w are dielectric constants of solvent and water respectively, and r_+ and r_- the radii of cation and anion taken as 0.97 and 2.89Å for Cd^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} ions respectively¹².

The electrostatic part of entropy of transfer is given by equation (14),

$$\Delta S_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} = -\frac{Ne^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{D_s\theta_s} - \frac{1}{D_w\theta_w} \right] \left[\frac{1}{r_+} + \frac{1}{r_-} \right] \quad (14)$$

where the values of θ_s and θ_w can be evaluated from the slopes of linear plots of $\ln D$ against T for water and respective mannitol + water mixture using relation (15),

$$d \ln D/dT = -\frac{1}{\theta} \quad (15)$$

where θ is a constant characteristic of the medium⁷.

From the knowledge of $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ and $\Delta S_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ the electrostatic part of the enthalpy change $\Delta H_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ can be computed as

$$\Delta H_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} = \Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} + T\Delta S_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta} \quad (16)$$

The chemical contributions of $\Delta G_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta}$, $\Delta H_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta}$ and $\Delta S_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta}$ are obtained by subtracting the respective electrostatic contribution values from the molal quantities and these values at 298 K are recorded in Table 7. It has been found that $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^{\theta}$ and $\Delta G_{t,\text{ch}}^{\theta}$ are increasingly positive in all mannitol + water mixtures, indicating that transfer of cadmium sulphate from water to mannitol + water mixtures is not favoured as far as chemical interactions are concerned. This suggests that all mannitol + water mixtures are less

basic than pure water and this increases with increasing mannitol content. The electrostatic contributions of enthalpy and entropy of transfer go on decreasing with increasing mannitol content. The same is the trend for chemical contribution. It can be inferred that the chemical contribution or solvation predominates over electrostatic factor, resulting in an overall unfavourable effect on the transfer process from water to mannitol + water mixtures. The negative values of these parameters may be due to the introduction of the structural order on microscopic scale in mannitol + water mixtures.

Table 7. Electrical and chemical parts of the thermodynamic quantities accompanying the transfer of cadmium sulphate from water to mannitol + water mixtures at 298 K

Mannitol wt. %	$\Delta G_{t,el}^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G_{t,ch}^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H_{t,el}^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H_{t,ch}^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_{t,el}^{\circ}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_{t,ch}^{\circ}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
5	0.08	0.76	-0.46	0.11	-1.81	0.16
15	0.36	1.18	-1.41	1.04	-5.93	-0.53
25	0.64	1.71	-1.64	0.12	-7.65	-5.48

Experimental

Water used for preparation of solutions had specific conductance of the order of 10⁻⁶ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Cadmium sulphate was crystallised from distilled water. Mercurous sulphate was prepared by the reported method¹³. Mannitol and mercury (A.R.) were used as such. Cadmium-amalgam used in the cell was prepared as described earlier¹⁴. All solutions were prepared by weight.

The e.m.f. cell consisted of two pyrex glass tubes joined at the centre by another tube which was provided with a stop-cock. At the bottom of two pyrex tubes two platinum wires were fixed whose contact with the inside solution of the cell was made with mercury. The platinum wire in one limb of the cell was covered with amalgam and that in the other with Hg/Hg₂SO₄(s) and then they were covered with electrolyte solution. A 1/10th degree thermometer was dipped inside the solution in the cell. The cell

was connected to a potentiometer (± 0.1 mV). The cell was placed in an air-thermostat (± 0.05). Stop-cock was opened and kept it as such for ~2 h until the equilibrium of the cell was set up and the constant e.m.f. was recorded. E.m.f. was measured at different temperatures and concentrations. The e.m.f. was used for estimation of activity coefficient and various thermodynamic functions of transfer from water to respective mannitol + water solutions. The concentrations of solutions were occasionally checked after the experiments were performed simultaneously in each case and they generally agreed within 0.5 mV.

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